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PLACE NAMES IN THE LITERARY DISCOURSE: ARGENTINIAN NARRATIVE OF IDENTITY

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ABSTRACT

The article examines the functioning of place names in fiction and their connection with real geographical objects. Based on the texts of outstanding Argentine writers Jorge Luis Borges and Julio Cortázar, the article analyzes the origin of toponyms recorded in their works, the historical context and the features of their use in personal artistic discourse. Particular attention is paid to cases when authors use place names in a metaphorical meaning, as well as the role of toponyms in the narrative of national Argentine identity. The results of the analysis showed that toponyms in fiction perform not only a nominative, locative, but also a symbolic function, enhancing the aesthetic effect of the narrative, creating allusions to real historical events, acting as key markers of national self-consciousness, a value component of national identity and simultaneously conveying philosophical ideas of being.

Key words: toponym, textual analysis, historical context, literary text, national identity, Argentina.

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1. Introduction

Etymology, internal form, morphological structure, derivational and discursive resources of geographical names – this is far from a complete list of issues that are of interest both for traditional toponymic studies and for new studies, which include the reconstruction and interpretation of the linguistic picture of the world, i.e. the features of the worldview of society enshrined in linguistic signs [1, p. 468], as well as the role of toponyms in conveying ideas of national identity [2].

National identity in modern scientific discourse is interpreted as a polysemantic concept in which political, civil, territorial, ethnic, and linguistic components intersect [3, p. 405].

Toponyms in a literary text serve as an important tool for creating an image of space and chronotope, according to M.M. Bakhtin [4], be it a realistic topos or a fantasy world. The choice of toponyms may be determined by an author's desire for authenticity, as well as the desire to bring additional meaning through stable associations with real geographical objects or to give a sense of authenticity to fictional toponyms.

Many scientific works are devoted to the functions of toponyms in fiction¹.

The material for our study is the fiction texts of outstanding Argentine writers of the 20th century - J.L. Borges and J. Cortázar, whose artistic discourse serves

¹See, for example, Berenkova, V. M. Functions of toponyms in fantasy literature // Science today: collection of scientific papers based on the materials of the international scientific and practical conference, Vologda, October 24, 2014 / Scientific center "Dispute". Volume Part 4. - Vologda: "Izdatelsky dom Vologzhanin", 2014. - Pp. 19-20.; Kondrashova Kozmina, V. N., Shustrova E.N. Evaluative and characterizing function of toponyms in English-language genre literature // Philological sciences. Questions of theory and practice. - 2021. - Vol. 14, No. 10. - Pp. 3094-3099.; Zhalilov, A. Stylistic functions of toponyms in fiction (based on obsolete toponyms in T. Sydykbekov's novels) // News of higher education institutions (Kyrgyzstan). - 2010. - No.

5. - P. 301-302.; Petrov, A.V. Toponyms as an expressive means in the northern text // Philological regional studies. - 2010. - No. 1-2 (3-4). - P. 48-53; Maslov, V.A. Linguistic and regional studies function of toponyms in the work of J. C. Jerome "Three Men in a Boat, Not Counting the Dog" // Lingvodidactics and intercultural communication: current issues and research prospects: Collection of scientific articles. - Cheboksary: Chuvash State Pedagogical University named after I.Ya. Yakovlev, 2018. - P. 379-385.; Yukhnova, A.K. Functioning of proper names in Guy de Maupassant's novel "Life" // Bulletin of the Magistracy. - 2015. - No. 6-1(45). - P. 79-81. and others.

as a reliable source for deriving markers of Argentine national identity [5]. Jorge Luís Borges (1899-1986) occupies a special place among the masters of words. Alien to the "magical realism", on the wave of which Latin American literature rapidly entered world literature, Borges is an intellectual writer who passionately loved his native Argentina, which, in addition to literary and artistic creativity, was embodied in works on the peculiarities of the Spanish language of Argentines and in studies of the gaucho subculture. At the same time, he is a unique creator, freely operating with the treasures of world literature and creating from them a bizarre pattern of his texts [6, p. 206]. Julio Cortázar (1914-1984), on the contrary, entered world literature precisely on the wave of the boom of Latin American literature, creating his own unique idiolect with the symbolism of topoi and labyrinths [7; 8].

The authors of the article proceed from the premise that any text has such properties as coherence and integrity, and in its structure the parts of the whole have their own roles [9, p. 7]. Any artistic text universally implements the following parameters of textuality: 1) cohesion; 2) coherence; 3) intentionality; 4) acceptability; 5) informativity; 6) situationality; 7) intertextuality, and along with them reveals such specific parameters as imagery, conventionality, autosemanticity, continuity and contextuality.²

The hypothesis of the article is that the appeal to toponyms in the structure of a fiction text creates a mental image and cultural aura of the complex aesthetics of the fiction text, and toponyms in a fiction text serve as a tool for solving the author's aesthetic problems: linguapoetic and ideological-artistic. The main research methods are linguistic commentary, parametric analysis of textuality, comparative method as applied to toponyms, analysis of the interaction of cultural-semiotic and semantic components of toponyms in the structure of a fiction text. The object of the study is toponyms in the fiction texts of J. L. Borges and J. Cortázar. The subject of the study is the structural-semantic and compositional organization of toponyms in the space of a fiction text against the background of similarities and differences with real toponyms.

The specific research objectives of the article are to identify toponyms found in the artistic discourse of Borges and Cortázar and to establish:

- their correspondence to real geographical objects;
- the historical and cultural context of the origin of real toponyms that entered the artistic space of the texts of both writers;
- interpret their functions as markers of national and cultural identity.

The research procedure includes a comparative analysis of data from literary texts with the statistics of the GeoNames system³, the study of historical documents and works of art where these place names are found, and the interpretation of their cultural and his-

torical connotations. Consequently, the research methodology is based on the interaction of the linguo-semiotic and functional-semantic approaches of modern text linguistics and onomastics.

2. Toponyms as markers of national identity on the geographical map and in artistic discourse

In artistic discourse, national identity interacts with the created and aesthetically motivated semiotics of objective historical events, national cultural space, nationally marked and linguaculturally significant representations of an ethnic group, and the author's idiolect [10, p. 40].

Let us consider specific examples of toponyms in this context, interpret their origin and conduct their textual analysis.

Adrogué. Real geographical object: a city in Buenos Aires Province, Argentina. Founded in 1873, it is named after the politician Esteban Adrogué and is known for its architecture and parks. In Borges' short story *El otro duelo* the creation of a realistic topos, where two writers are in conversation, at the expense of the real toponym Adrogué, is preceded by a contrast with the tragic story of the duel between two gauchos, which emphasizes the timeless context of human impulses and passions:

"Hace ya tantos años que Carlos Reyles , hijo del novelista, me refirió la historia en Adrogué, en un atardecer de verano." [11].

El Maldonado. Real geographical object: El Maldonado /Arroyo Maldonado — watercourse in Buenos Aires province and Buenos Aires autonomous city, in central - east region Argentina. In the following excerpt from Borges' story *Hombre de la Esquina Rosada* written in the genre of Argentine milonga, we observe this name three times, and it acts not only as a precise topographic sign, but also, according to the aesthetics of the story, as a symbol of the border and fate. Noteworthy in the aspect of Argentine identity is the adverb *dende* from lunfardo, which creates an aura of Argentine identity, and not the normative common Spanish *donde*:

" Los muchachos it 's crazy dende temprano en el sal ó n de Julia , what? era un galp o n de chapas de cinc , entre el camino de Gauna y el Maldonado ."

"Se empinó de golpe hacia atrás y voló el cuchillo derecho y fue a perderse ajuera, en el Maldonado."

"—Vos siempre has de servir de estorbo, pendejo —me rezongó al pasar, no sé si para desahogarse, o ajeno. Agarró el lado más oscuro, el del Maldonado; no lo volví a ver más." [12].

Banfield. Real geographical object: a district in Buenos Aires. Named after the British engineer Edward Banfield, who participated in the construction of the railway. In the autobiographical story *Los venenos* Julio Cortázar uses the toponym *Banfield* not so much to denote a precise topos, but rather to convey an internal state and family drama, with the ants becoming its superficial material embodiment, shading the deep side of

² According to the terminology of R.A. Bogrand and V. Dressler. URL: https://knowledge.allbest.ru/languages/3c0a65625b2ac68a5d43b89521206c37_0.html : access date: 08/26/2025.

³ GeoNames. URL: www.geonames.org

the internal conflict. Thus, a real place name acquires symbolic meaning universality:

"Conocíamos bien las hormigas de Bánfield, las hormigas negras que se van comiendo todo, hacen los hormigueros en la tierra, en los zócalos, o en ese pedazo misterioso donde una casa se hunde en el suelo, allí hacen agujeros disimulados pero no pueden esconder su fila negra que va y viene trayendo pedacitos de hojas, y los pedacitos de hojas eran las plantas del jardín, por eso mamá y tío Carlos se habían decidido a comprar la máquina para acabar con las hormigas."

"A la noche tía Rosa le dijo a mamá si mi primo Hugo podía quedarse a pasar toda la semana en Bánfield porque estaba un poco débil de la pleuresía y necesitaba sol." [13].

Chacarita. Real geographical object: a district in Buenos Aires, Argentina. *Chacarita* is also the name of a cemetery, one of the largest in the city. The name comes from the Spanish word "*chacra*" (farm), as it was a rural area in the 19th century. The cemetery was founded in 1871 during a yellow fever epidemic. In Julio Cortázar's novel "*Rayuela*", the mention of the *Chacarita* cemetery, in addition to the precise topographic Argentine reality, conveys the writer's thoughts on life and death, on the relationship between the eternal and the everyday, as in the naming of the football club *Chacarita Juniors*. In any case, the examples show the metaphysical use of the cemetery name in Cortázar's idiolect:

"En Chacarita, los muertos no descansan, solo esperan su turno para volver a la conversación".

"Todo iba tan bien que Traveler bajó los ojos y se puso a tamborilear en la mesa. El mozo, que los conocía mucho, se acercó para discutir sobre Ferrocarril Oeste, y Oliveira apostó diez pesos a la mano de Chacarita Juniors."

"—Lo del cementerio no se le ocurrió ni a Espronceda—dijo Traveler—. No me vas a negar que la analogía entre la Chacarita y un archivo..." [14].

The Argentine flavor is also inherent in the following context from Borges' story *Historia de Rosendo Juárez*: the use of forms of Rioplatense *voseo*, the lunfardo jargon spoken by the compadritos, and the mention of the *Chacarita* cemetery becomes a metonymic designation of death:

"—Ya sé que no le tenés miedo, pero pensalo bien. Una de dos: o lo matás y vas a la sombra, o él te mata y vas a la Chacarita." [15].

Chacabuco, Maipú, Arequipa. In Argentina, the oikonyms of small and medium-sized settlements are of Indian origin, and they have roots in the Indian languages of the Mapuche, Chon, Aymara, Quechua, Guaraní, Huarpe, and other groups [16, p. 74]. Real geographical objects: *Chacabuco* is a city in Argentina, in the province of Buenos Aires. The name *Chacabuco* comes from two Araucanian words: *chacay* — thorny tree (*Colletia domiana*) and *buvo* — slope. *Maipú* is a city in Argentina, in the province of Buenos Aires. The name in the Mapuche language means "place where the sun sets". *Arequipa* is a city in Peru, a major cultural and economic center. The name of the city comes from

the phrase *ari qhipa* in Aymara, where *ari* means "summit, mountain top" and *qhipa* means "behind", which together translates to "(place) behind the summit", referring to the nearby Misti volcano.

In the following example from Borges's story *La señora Mayor* The writer places three place names in one sentence, the allusive power of which is so great in the consciousness of Argentines that the deciphering of the historical events of the battles of Tucumán (1812), Salta (1813), Chacabuco (1817) and Maipú (1818), despite the laconicism of the linguistic means, acquires a great impact, contrasting with the documentary style of the narrative:

"Nacido en la parroquia de la Merced, hijo de hacendados de la provincia, fue promovido a alférez en el hey, hey de los Andes, milicias Chacabuco, en la derrot de Cancha Rayada, en Maipú y, dos años después, en Arequipa." [17].

Cerro Alto. Real geographical object: a mountain in Argentina, in the central Andes. In Borges's short story *La señora mayor* refers to the Battle of Cerro Alto. This is a fictional battle, a product of Borges's artistic imagination, which has become in the aesthetics of the text a metaphor for the numerous battles in Argentina and South America that took the lives of thousands of South Americans. The fictional onomastic sign becomes the basis of Borges's myth and acquires a generalizing, universal meaning of national history, the relationship between memory and oblivion:

"A principios de abril del 23 ocurriría el célebre combate de Cerro Alto que, por haberse librado en el valle, suele denominarse también de Cerro Bermejo."

"La primera guerra europea, que le hizo detestar a los alemanes, de los que sabía muy poco, fue menos real para ella que la revolución del noventa y que la carga de Cerro Alto."

"El presidente envió a su edecán, un señor muy amable, que dijo que para él era todo un honor estrechar la mano de la hija del héroe de Cerro Alto."

"Pienso en los muertos de Cerro Alto, pienso en los hombres olvidados de América y de España que perecieron bajo los cascos de los caballos; pienso que la última víctima de ese tropel de lanzas en el Perú sería, más de un siglo después, una señora anciana." [17].

Ayacucho. Real geographical object: a city in Argentina, in the province of Buenos Aires, named after the battle. The Battle of Ayacucho (Spanish: *Batalla de Ayacucho*) was a decisive battle of the Spanish Revolutionary War in the Americas, fought on December 9, 1824, on the plain of Ayacucho in Peru. The name comes from the Quechua language: *Ayak'uchu*, where *aya* is "death" or "soul", and *k'uchu* is "corner". Its original name (the city was founded in 1540 as *San Juan de la Frontera de Huamanga* or *Huamanga*) was officially changed by Simón Bolívar from "*Huamanga*" to "*Ayacucho*" by the decree on February 15, 1825, in memory of the Battle of Ayacucho, which finally established the full independence of the young Peruvian Republic. The allusion to Ayacucho in the following example clearly illustrates Borges's idiolect: through the apparent simplicity and brevity of a single toponym, to

convey a "garden of forking paths" of reflections on national identity and personal history. This is not only an accurate indication of the place and the famous battle of Ayacucho, but also an incentive to think about the eternal questions of existence:

"Éste, a la cabeza de un regimiento de húsares colombianos, decidió la incierta contienda de sables y de lanzas, que preparó la no menos famosa acción de Ayacucho, en la que también se batió." [17].

Ituzaingó. Real geographical object: a city in Argentina. This South American toponym comes from the Guaraní language. The name to the city in Argentinian province of Buenos Aires is given in honor of the Uruguayan town of Ituzaingó. In Argentina, in honor of the Battle of Ituzaingó, which the Argentines consider their victory, the following objects are named: a municipality in the province of Buenos Aires, the administrative center of this municipality, a football club, a department in the province of Corrientes, the administrative center of this department. The Battle of Ituzaingó (in Brazil it is known as the Battle of Passo do Rosário) was the largest battle of the Argentina–Brazilian War of 1826–1828, which took place on February 20, 1827, between the allies (Argentine troops and rebels of the Eastern Coast (Uruguay)) and the Brazilian Imperial Army. In Borges's short story *La señora mayor* the toponym Ituzaingó, performing a locative-nominative function, becomes a historical marker of the identity of the Argentines and a symbol of their military valor:

"En ésta recibió una herida. El 27 le fue dado actuar con demuedo en Ituzaingó, a las órdenes inmediatas de Alvear." [17].

Montevideo. Real geographical object: *Montevideo*, the capital of Uruguay. In an example from Borges' story *La señora mayor*, despite its compactness, recreates important symbols of the historical context of the history of Argentina and Uruguay: it mentions Manuel Oribe, the second president of Uruguay (1835–1838), Guerra Grande ("Great War"), the civil war in Uruguay from 1839 to 1851. The conflict was triggered by an armed clash between Uruguayan and Argentine troops. The use of the toponym *Montevideo* in the text becomes both a realistic setting and a symbol of resistance:

"En el decurso de la Guerra Grande, murió en Montevideo, plaza sitiada por los blancos de Oribe." [17].

Buenos Aires. Real geographical object: the city of *Buenos Aires*, the capital of Argentina. Borges himself emphasized that he could not live in any other city except Buenos Aires, and he is aware of his connection with it [18, pp. 53–54, 124]. In the story *La señora mayor*, developing the themes of collective and personal memory, Buenos Aires also acts as a historical topos:

"A fines del 53 la viuda del coronel y sus hijas se fijaron en Buenos Aires", and as a personified chronotope, connecting, according to Bakhtin, space and time: *"No salía de su casa; quizá no sospechaba que Buenos Aires había ido cambiando y creciendo."* [17].

Lomas de Zamora Real geographical object: a city located in the district of the same name, in the province of Buenos Aires (Argentina). *Lomas de Zamora* is an example of an Argentine suburb, a symbol of its faded former greatness. The mention of this place name is associated with such cultural codes of Argentine identity as the loss of former greatness, which can be traced in the fate of the heroines of Borges' story *Laseñora Mayor*:

"Contaban con una pensión, que siempre les llegaba con atraso, y con el alquiler de un terreno — único resto de la estancia, antes vasta — en Lomas de Zamora." [17].

Street names in Borges' story *La señora mayor* also have symbolic meanings. This is a kind of "nomenclature of Señora de Jáuregui" from the places of her memory, unrealistic, fictitious names for a contemporary, opposed to the real topography of Buenos Aires and creating a contrast between the real chronotope and the personal chronotope, which again develops the themes of memory and the relationship between personal and national identity:

"La nomenclatura de la señora de Jáuregui siguió siendo anticuada; hablaba de la calle de las Artes, de la calle del Temple, de la calle Buen Orden, de la calle de la Piedad, de las dos Calles Largas, de la plaza del Parque y de los Portones." [17].

In the following example one can see the name *la plaza del Once* from the dialect of the inhabitants of Buenos Aires, while its official name is *Plaza Miserere*, which, in combination with other means, conveys ideas of nostalgia for the past:

"Los bueyes de las carretas descansarían en la plaza del Once y las violetas muertas aromarían las quintas de Barracas." [17].

Fray Bentos. Real geographical object: a town in Uruguay named after a local Franciscan monk. *Fray* is Spanish for "brother" (about the monk) [19, p. 63]. This quiet town was once home to a food brand founded in 1863, and its industrial landscape is now a World Heritage Site. The main character of the Borges's story *Funes el memorioso*, possessing phenomenal capabilities in memory of "compadrito" Irineo Funes, is almost a prototype of a superman and lives in the remote *Fray Bentos*:

"Pedro Leandro Ipuche ha escrito que Funes era un precursor de los superhombres; "Un Zarathustra cimarrón y vernáculo"; no lo discuto, pero no hay que olvidar que era también un compadrito de Fray Bentos, con ciertas incurables limitaciones".

It is in *Fray Bentos* that the storyteller periodically comes to tell the story of Irineo Funes and his incredible abilities:

"Los años ochenta y cinco y ochenta y seis veraneamos en la ciudad de Montevideo. El ochenta y siete volví a Fray Bentos." [20].

Thus, in Borges's story *Funes el memorioso* *Fray Bentos*, from a provincial place name becomes a symbol of the opposition between the sublime and the mundane.

Guayaquil. Real geographical object: the most populous city in Ecuador, located approximately 250 kilometers southwest of the country's capital Quito on

the Guayas River. Founded in 1538. V. A. Nikonov associates this oikonym with the ethnonym of the Guayquil Indian tribe [21, p. 112]. E. M. Pospelov believes that the location of the city on the Guayas River allows us to think about the primacy of the hydronym, which may be associated with the name in the Tupi language *Guaya* ("guayas" (river) + "quil" (valley)) [22, p. 126]. There is also a widespread legend according to which the name is derived from the names of the Indian chieftain Guayas and his wife Quil, who were killed by the Spanish conquerors.

On July 26, 1822, in Guayaquil, Bolívar, as a representative of the North of Spanish-speaking South America, met with José de San Martín, as a representative of the South, to discuss the possibility of joint action, as well as the political future and relations of the recently formed independent republics. Due to different visions of the future of the colonies that had declared independence, the generals were unable to agree among themselves. This meeting and the interpretation of the reasons why, as a result of it, "General San Martín completely abandoned all his highest aspirations and handed over the destinies of America into the hands of Bolívar," who completed its liberation from the Spaniards, are the subject of Borges' short story "Guayaquil," where the toponym of the same name becomes a multi-vector symbol of the recurrence of situations and collisions of military and personal conflicts:

"Inútil destacar el valor de este documento en el que Bolívar ha revelado, siquiera parcialmente, lo sucedido en Guayaquil".

"Esas generalidades pomposas me fastidiaron y observé secamente que dentro del enigma que nos rodea, la entrevista de Guayaquil, en la que el general San Martín renunció a la mera ambición y dejó el destino de América en manos de Bolívar es también un enigma que puede merecer el estudio".

"— Acaso las palabras que cambiaron fueron triviales. Dos hombres se enfrentaron en Guayaquil; si uno se impuso, fue por su mayor voluntad, no por juegos dialécticos".

"Agregó con una sonrisa:

— Words, words, words. Shakespeare, insuperado maestro de las palabras, las desdeñaba. En Guayaquil o en Buenos Aires, en Praga, siempre cuentan menos que las personas." [23].

Morón. Real geographical object: a city in Argentina in the province of Buenos Aires. There is no consensus among historians about the origin of the city's name. Possible options include the names of the protagonists: Diego Morón, whose widow, Isabel Torres Briseño, was one of the landowners of this area in the 18th century; Pedro Morán, another local landowner; San Pedro de Morón, the patron saint of the local mayor of the time; and the town of Morón de la Frontera in Andalusia, Spain, where many of the original settlers came from. In the following example, the repetition of the toponym Morón creates a rhythmic pattern of the phrase and fixes the topos of the narrative in the reader's mind, shading the temporal nature of the described collisions:

"Dicen (lo cual es improbable) que la historia fue referida por Eduardo, el menor de los Nelson, en el

velorio de Cristián, el mayor, que falleció de muerte natural, hacia mil ochocientos noventa y tantos, en el partido de Morón".

"Había llovido; los caminos estaban muy pesados y serían las once de la noche cuando llegaron a Morón".

"Cristián se fue a Morón; en el palenque de la casa que sabemos reconoció al overo de Eduardo. Entró; adentro estaba el otro, esperando turno." [24].

Paysandú. Real geographical object: *Paysandú* is the fourth most populous city in Uruguay, the largest city and the capital of the *Paysandú* department. It was founded in 1749 as a Jesuit fort on the banks of the Uruguay River. In 1865, the city became one of the arenas of the struggle of the Uruguayans under the leadership of General Leandro Gómez against the invasion of Brazil. The city is located on the left bank of the Uruguay River, and on the opposite bank is the Argentine city of Colón. The two cities are connected by the international bridge "General Artigas", which was opened on December 10, 1975. According to one version, the name comes from the words *Paso del Sandu*. "Paso" in Spanish means "crossing" (there used to be a crossing for cattle in this place), and *Sandu* is the name of the place. There is also a legend that in 1772, on the site of modern *Paysandú*, a Jesuit monk named Pay Sandu, supposedly born in Buenos Aires, founded a Jesuit mission, which included 12 families of local aborigines. But this legend has been questioned. In 1919, a certain Baldomero Vidal specifically studied church archives and found no traces confirming the life of the monk. However, in subsequent years, mentions of *Paysandú* were found even in older documents, before 1772. Namely, a map was discovered that was drawn up in 1749 by the Jesuit missionary priest José Quiroga, on which the fort of *Paysandú* is marked on the present-day site of the city. The year 1749 is considered the year of the foundation of *Paysandú*. In Borges's story *La secta del Fénix* this place name outwardly creates a specific geographical attribution of the action, but from an ideological and artistic point of view, it is generalized to the idea of the universality of the secret knowledge of the sect, that is, again the toponym from a geographical indicator becomes an artistic symbol:

"Son todo para todos, como el Apóstol; días pasados el doctor Juan Francisco Amaro, de Paysandú, ponderó la facilidad con que se acriollaban." [25]

Plaza de Mayo. Real geographical object: the central square of the capital Argentina cities Buenos Aires. It has existed since 1580 and is the place where Buenos Aires began to be rebuilt. In 1810, the main events of the May Revolution took place in the square, after which it was named. On September 13, 1816, Argentina's independence was proclaimed in the Plaza de Mayo, and on October 21, 1860, the adoption of the Argentine Constitution was announced.

In the following excerpts from Julio Cortázar's short story *Después del almuerzo*, the stringing together of place names creates a dramatic effect, with the Plaza de Mayo, the most famous and symbolically laden place in the capital, becoming the epicentre of a dramatic personal story:

"A esa hora si yo hubiera viajado solo me habría largado del tranvía para seguir a pie hasta el centro, para mí no es nada ir a pie desde el Once a Plaza de Mayo, una vez que me tomé el tiempo le puse justo treinta y dos minutos, claro que corriendo de a ratos y sobre todo al final".

"A mí me gusta mucho la Plaza de Mayo, cuando me hablan del centro pienso en seguida en la Plaza de Mayo".

"Por eso pensé que lo mejor era llevarlo a la Plaza de Mayo, lejos de los autos y los colectivos, y sentarnos un rato ahí hasta que fuera hora de ir volviendo a casa".

"A la larga conseguí que se le pasara el capricho de quedarse ahí parado, y seguimos por San Martín hasta la esquina de la Plaza de Mayo".

"Lo malo es que para llegar a la Plaza de Mayo hay que cruzar siempre alguna calle con mucho tráfico, en Cangallo y Bartolomé Mitre no había sido tan difícil, pero ahora yo estaba a punto de renunciar..."

"Compré manises y caramelos, le fui dando de las dos cosas y estábamos bastante bien con ese sol que hay por la tarde en la Plaza de Mayo y la gente que va de un lado a otro." [26].

Quebracho. Real geographical object: *Quebracho Herrado* is a small Argentine settlement in the east of the province of Córdoba, near which in November 1840 the army of Rosas defeated the rebel troops. The Battle of Quebracho Herrado took place on November 28, 1840. It was a victory of the Argentine Federal Army led by the former President of Uruguay, Brigadier General Manuel Oribe, over the unitary army led by Brigadier General Juan Lavalle. The name is typical of South America in general and comes from the collective name of three subtropical tree species from South America, quebracho, quebracho or quebracho (*Schinopsis lorentzii*), their wood and bark. Quebracho is a fusion of the Spanish lexemes *quebrar* and *hacha* ("to break" and "axe"): the wood of these trees is very hard and durable [27, p. 183]. At the beginning of the 19th century, among the meadows and thorny bushes that covered the interior of Argentina, next to a country road connecting Córdoba with the province of Santa Fé, there grew a grove of quebracho trees. A horseshoe was nailed to the trunk of the tallest of them, marking the border between the provinces of Córdoba and Santa Fé. The name *Quebracho Herrado* comes from this tree and means "shoed quebracho". In Borges's short story *Funes el memorioso*, the nomination of "the actions of Quebracho" creates a concrete historical allusion to the plot and precedes the mention of the waters of the Rio Negro, which become a symbol of the flow of time and memories in time:

"Sabía las formas de las nubes australes del amanecer del treinta de abril de mil ochocientos ochenta y dos y podía compararlas en el recuerdo con las vetas de un libro en pasta española que solo había mirado una vez y con las líneas de la espuma que un remo levantó en el Río Negro la víspera de la acción del Quebracho." [20].

Rivadavia. Real geographical object: *Avenida Rivadavia* — an avenue in the city of Buenos Aires. It runs through the city from east to west, dividing it into

two almost equal parts. The avenue is named after Bernardino Rivadavia (1780–1845), a politician who served as the first President of Argentina or President of the United Provinces of the Rio de la Plata between February 8, 1826 and August 9, 1827. Along the avenue are the Pink House (the residence of the President of Argentina), the Bank of the Argentine Nation, the Cathedral, the Palace of Congresses, Rivadavia Park and the Basilica of San José de Flores. In Borges's famous short story *El Sur*, which recreates the debate about what Argentina should be: northern, "European" or southern, gaucho-Creole, Rivadavia, being a real topographic sign, acts as a symbolic border or axis of the two components of Argentine identity:

"Nadie ignora que el Sur empieza del otro lado de Rivadavia. Dahlmann solía repetir que ello no es una convención y que quien atraviesa esa calle entra en un mundo más antiguo y más firme." [28].

Tacuarembó. Real geographical object: a river in the Eastern Republic of Uruguay, the largest right tributary of the Rio Negro. Also *Tacuarembó* is a city in the north-central part of Uruguay, the administrative center of the department of the same name. The name comes from the nomination of the settlement located in the vicinity of the river *Tacuaremboty*, which in the Guarani language means "river of reed beds". The mention of the *Tacuarembó* river by Borges creates the illusion of authenticity in contrast to the fictitious names *Tlön* and *Uqbar*:

"Una creciente del río Tacuarembó nos obligó a probar (y a sobrellevar) esa rudimentaria hospitalidad." [29].

Talcahuano. Real geographical object: a city and seaport in Chile, founded in 1764. The city is named after the Araucanian chieftain Talcahueñu, who inhabited the region when the Spanish arrived. In Mapudungun, the language of the indigenous Mapuche people, *Talcahuano* means "thunder sky". As in the previous example, the mention of a toponym creates the effect of locative credibility:

"Ese nombre le doy porque bajo ese nombre lo conocieron por calles y por casas de Talcahuano, de Santiago de Chile y de Valparaíso, hacia 1850, y es justo que lo asuma otra vez, ahora que retorna a estas tierras —siquiera en calidad de mero fantasma y de pasatiempo del sábado". [30].

Tapalquén. Real geographical object: an Argentine city located in the center of the province of Buenos Aires. Its name in the Mapudungun language means "water with reeds", and in Borges's story *El encuentro* this toponym symbolizes the peace and culture of the gaucho:

"Olave prosiguió sin apuro, como si pensara en voz alta:

— Una de las dagas tenía el gavián en forma de U. Dagas como ésas hubo dos que se hicieron famosas: la de Moreira y la de Juan Almada, por Tapalquén." [31].

Turdera. Real geographical object: a city in the Argentine Republic, located in the southern part of Greater Buenos Aires. Founded on January 30, 1910, when the first settlers laid the foundation stone of the Church of San Pablo. In 1908, the owners of the land,

the sisters María Eugenia and Inés Turdera, who received it from their uncle, Eduardo Puig, began dividing the territory and handing it over to the commune to lay out streets and build squares, schools, churches and public buildings. Tordera, which was declared a city in 1974, is the smallest town in the Lomas de Zamora district. María Eugenia and Inés Turdera were natives of Catalonia, more specifically of the town of Tordera, which is pronounced Turdera in Catalan. In Borges's short story *La intrusa* the mention of Turdera brings to the story the features of an urban legend about the fatal decision of two brothers to kill a woman:

"Años después, volvieron a contármela en Tordera, donde había acontecido".

"En Turdera los llamaban los Nilsen".

"En Turdera, los Nilsen, perdidos hasta entonces en la mañana (que también era una rutina) de aquel monstroso amor, quisieron reanudar su antigua vida de hombres entre hombres." [24].

Urdinarrain. Real geographical object: a town in the central southern part of Entre Ríos Province, Argentina. The town's current name is a tribute to General Manuel Antonio Urdinarrain (1801–1868), who fought alongside local caudillos Francisco Ramírez and Justo José de Urquiza. In Borges' short story *El indigno* the "unworthy" fact of the hero's birth in the city of Urdinarrain creates an image of the hinterland, opposed to the capital Buenos Aires:

"Nací en Urdinarrain, de la que apenas guardo memoria; cuando mis padres se vinieron a Buenos Aires, para abrir una tienda, yo era muy chico." [32].

3. Discussion of results

Most of the toponyms in the works of J.L. Borges and J. Cortázar have clear historical roots and at the same time acquire numerous symbolic meanings as allusions to the history of Argentina and South America, and also function as philosophical symbols, creating coherence and integrity of the narrative. The use of place names by Borges gives them the function of a full-fledged participant in the narrative, on which philosophical ideas are superimposed. Borges's Argentine toponyms range from specific geographical names – urbanonyms, as in the poem "*La fundación mitológica de Buenos Aires*" [33] to diffuse nominations "en el sur de la provincia de Buenos Aires" (in the south of the province of Buenos Aires) in the mini-story "*La trama*" [6]. Borges's idiolex contains many fictitious toponyms, such as *Tlön, Uqbar, Orbis Tertius* in the story of the same name (1941), which in his idiolex acquire features of decorativeness and at the same time reality. In Julio Cortázar's works, the use of toponyms combines childhood impressions, experienced real-life collisions, complex layers of psychological meanings and the grotesqueness of their depiction.

Despite the fragmentariness and randomness of the text examples chosen for the illustrative material of the article, they allow us to see the most essential features of the role of toponyms in the aesthetic integrity of the artistic text. Based on our analysis, we can identify several main functions of toponyms in works of art.

1. Realistic – accurate reproduction of real places for authenticity.

2. Symbolic – using names to create allusions (for example, *Plaza de Mayo* as a symbol of political struggle).

3. Metaphorical – the use of fictitious toponyms to convey ideological and aesthetic meanings (*la calle de las Artes, la calle del Temple, la calle Buen Orden, de la calle de la Piedad* and others as a reflection of the main character's anachronistic inner world in the story "La señora mayor" by Borges).

4. Identification – the use of toponyms as markers of national and cultural affiliation.

The use of toponyms in fiction is not limited to indicating the location of the action. Toponyms become symbols, codes of universalization: "in the south of the Province of Buenos Aires" in Borges's mini-story "*La trama*", as well as the collision of an unexpected betrayal of a close friend, can be attributed not only to Argentina, but to any corner of the Universe.

In the early 1980s, the Frenchman Pierre Nora introduced the concept of "places of memory" (*Lieux de mémoire*), denoting the unity of the spiritual and the material. Many of the toponyms discussed in the article refer to key events in national history, turning into "places of memory." For example, *Ituzaingó* in Argentine artistic discourse, it is not just a city, but a symbol of victory and sovereignty, referring to the struggle for independence. The mention of such a toponym evokes in the reader's memory a heroic national narrative. Similarly, *Plaza de Mayo* is not just a geographical point, but a concentrated symbol of political struggle, the memory of the "Mothers of the Plaza de Mayo"⁴ and the entire complex of tragic and heroic events in Argentine history in the 20th century.

The origin of a toponym is itself a marker of national identity. The presence of names with roots in indigenous languages (e.g., *Guayaquil*) creates a literary landscape that recalls pre-Columbian history and the multi-layered nature of Argentine and Latin American culture in general. On the other hand, toponyms given by colonizers or immigrants (*Bánfield, Fray Bentos*), point to a complex process of cultural synthesis, conflict and the formation of a new, synthetic identity. In artistic discourse, the clash of these layers can emphasize a crisis of identity or, conversely, its hybrid nature.

In the space of a literary text, place names create a "sense of place"⁵. For example, toponyms such as

⁴A social movement, associations of Argentine mothers whose children disappeared during the "Dirty War" policy of the military dictatorship, called the "National Reorganization Process", between 1976 and 1983 in Argentina. The movement takes its name from the central square of Buenos Aires - Plaza de Mayo, where, starting April 30, 1977, every Thursday, right in front of the government building, women whose children had disappeared without a trace began to gather. There is also a similar movement, the Grandmothers

of Plaza de Mayo (Spanish: Asociación Civil Abuelas de Plaza de Mayo), consisting of women whose daughters or daughters-in-law were pregnant at the time of their disappearance.

⁵ Yi Fu Tuan, a Chinese-American geographer, popularized the concept of Sense of Place in his book *Space and Place: The Perspective of Experience* (1977). It is a multifaceted concept that describes a person's emotional and psychological connection with a particular place.

Adrogué by Borges or *Chacarita* by Cortázar, serve the function of creating a deeply personal and at the same time universal “sense of place.” They describe not just a suburb or a cemetery, but archetypal spaces of nostalgia, memory, death, and oblivion that become part of the Argentine cultural code. Through these purely local names, the authors speak of universal human themes, but do so through the prism of national experience, which enhances the emotional impact on both the Latin American reader and serves as a transfer of knowledge for the foreign reader.

5. Conclusion

Thus, textual analysis has shown that most toponyms in the fiction have real cartographic analogues, but their use in the fictional discourse varies depending on the author's intention. **Real place names in the idioms of Borges and Cortázar are always functional.** They are active participants in their intellectual and intertextually rich narratives and convey deep philosophical ideas. Both writers created unique personal fictional discourses that allow us to reconstruct the Argentine national identity.

In the fictional text, the boundaries between real and fictional toponyms are erased. Interpersonal collisions placed in the Argentine topos by real toponyms or Argentine spatial coordinates reflecting the Argentine national identity undergo processes of universalization and turn into archetypes understood by representatives of any culture. In some cases, names are changed to enhance the aesthetic effect, in others they are preserved to link to the historical context.

As the analysis has shown, the key function of toponyms is their participation in the construction and transmission of national identity. They act as guardians of historical memory, linking the present with key events of the past; markers of cultural synthesis, reflecting the multi-layered ethnic and linguistic composition of Argentine society; symbols of national self-awareness, creating a unique “sense of place”; and instruments of criticism, allowing one to question official historical narratives.

Toponyms create a complex of historical, cultural and emotional associations in the reader's mind, forming and strengthening the idea of national identity.

The choice of illustrative text material for this article allowed us to see the most essential features of toponyms in the space of artistic text, the main ones of which, in the works of two outstanding Argentine masters of the word - J. L. Borges and J. Cortázar, is the organic combination of the concrete and the abstract. Toponyms become not only geographical references to the map, but a self-sufficient literary device, a means of expressing cultural codes, allowing writers to turn to collective memory and mythology.

We see the prospects of research in comparing toponymy in the artistic discourse of different countries and identifying common patterns in the use of toponyms to build identity, analyzing the reader's perception of real and fictional toponyms depending on the cultural background of the reader, and studying the role of microtoponyms (names of districts, streets, bars) in creating images of megacities in national literature.

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